
REVIEW: *LAST MEMORIES - A MDO TIBETAN TRIBAL LIVES: RDOR JAG AND THANG TA* BY
KLU THAR RGYAL ET AL.

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HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

Last Memories is the life accounts of two ordinary Tibetan individuals from a once-remote community in today's Mang ra (Guinan) County, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province in northwest PR China. Having lived during a critical historical period of social and political turmoil, experienced great changes in their lives, and witnessed the local historical transformation, these eyewitness accounts constitute a rich oral history of their home community. Supplemental materials give readers a more complete understanding of where and how the interviewees lived. These include maps identifying the community locations and sites of major events; lists of people, places, and Tibetan terms (IPA plus colloquial and Tibetan literary equivalents) for local livestock in the Appendix (herding culture); and photos of relevant figures, landscapes, houses, monasteries, local daily life, ceremonies and celebrations, food, and various objects. The author provides a list of materials for further reading in the Appendix, surely of interest to those who wish to explore Mang ra County history further.

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In *Last Memories*, Klu thar rgyal presents extraordinary life narratives of two "ordinary" individuals, the author's maternal grandfather, Bu lo (1929-2021, hereafter, Lo), and his maternal great-aunt, Lcags mo byams (b. 1940, Lo's wife's sister). His close relationship with both elders allowed him to explain aspects of their lives that would otherwise remain unknown.

Thanks to their advanced ages, *Last Memories* covers almost an entire century, including common life stories, e.g., childhood, dating, marriages, livestock herding, childcare, religious practices, banditry, revenge, conflicts with contemporary authorities over taxes, exile in other regions, and social unrest in the 1950s and later. These vivid firsthand accounts provide valuable materials in the fields of history, ethnography, social-political structures, economic transitions, Qinghai-Gansu and China history, and Tibetology.

The time this oral history encompasses is critical in China's contemporary history, particularly in the regions where the individuals in *Last Memories* have lived. 1949 was a turning point in the history of modern China, marking the start of a newly established political system - Communist China. Earlier, the family of Ma Bufang (1903-1975) controlled today's Qinghai Province for some four decades. Ma was notorious for brutally exploiting and oppressing locals causing massive suffering to ethnic Tibetans and other minorities in Qinghai and leaving unerasable scars in the memories of local people.¹

¹ Chen (2007) writes that Ma subjugated Bla brang Monastery twice, burned Gser lag (Sailihai) Monastery, suppressed Mgo log (Guoluo) seven times, killed Yul shul (Yushu) people, and crushed Reb gong (Tongren) tribes in the courses of multiple appalling massacres (210-230). Hundreds of locals from my natal home area fled to the Blab rang area during those troubled times to evade excessive taxation and military conscription under Ma's brutal rule. The author might have provided more information about Ma Bufang and A pa a lo, rulers of Qinghai and Bla brang areas, respectively, during the Guomindang (GMD) government (1919-1949). See Chen (2007), Fan (2014), and Cui et al. (2017) for more on Ma Bufang. A pa a lo's background is available in his autobiography (Huang 1989). Ma and A pa a lo, and their fathers, were rulers of their respective regions in northwest China during the Republic of China (1912-1949) period. The former's family ruled Qinghai Province,

Local Tibetans were eager for a better new era with the collapse of the Ma regime. However, unrest from the 1950s till the end of the Cultural Revolution (1976-1977) brought nationwide tragedy to China's citizens that Tibetans living in remote highland areas did not escape.

While historians have described certain aspects of major issues, such as political system changes in the region in the late 1940s, the Cultural Revolution, and powerful historical figures such as Ma Bufang, much less attention has been given to the lives of ordinary individuals living in remote communities on the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau. This further highlights the value of numerous social, political, and economic details that emerge in retelling two individuals' experiences during this period.

PART ONE: LO

The author chronologically presents the narrators' memories in two sections. Lo's life starts with birth in the local tribal leader's home in Tsha nag Community in 1929. Details of obligatory and frequent bandit raids by young men to demonstrate manhood and bravery are given, along with descriptions of the living situation of tent-living nomads. Such banditry traditions as when to start an attack, where to go, where not to go, and norms during a raid reveal social order (or its absence) are recounted in vivid detail. Lo describes conflicts between communities and local "heroes" and subsequent revenge killings at a time when banditry among community men was common.

and the latter controlled the Bla brang area of Gansu Province. Ma expanded his control with military attacks, threatening A pa a lo. Ma Bufang fled abroad with the establishment of the PRC in 1949, while A pa a lo stayed and cooperated with the new government in positions that included the vice governor of Gansu Province and the governor of Kan lho (Gannan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture. Consequently, Ma's contemporary Chinese official representation is that of a notorious anti-Communist and government warlord while A pa a lo is presented as a patriot.

¹ A pa a lo.

Lo also describes spirit mediums and divinations that were important in local life. Divinations by women are rare in many Tibetan communities, highlighting the value of two introduced divinations by women: (1) examining cracks in wheat figures resembling birds cooked in ash and 2) sheep dung pellets. These divination accounts illustrate the worry women at home had for their husbands and children for their fathers on dangerous bandit raids:

When cracks ran from the bottom to the ear, it meant that her husband had received the message she had sent through the bird-bread, indicating that he was safe, regardless of where he was.

As the woman was divining, her children surrounded her, eager for good news. When they found cracks to the ear of the bird, they happily examined it again and again and shouted, "Father is returning!" They kept it for a while and then competed to eat the auspicious bread bird (76).

Lo gives detailed accounts of local conditions, such as walking barefoot (shoes were rare), clothing, and ornaments. He encounters superpower manifestations rivaling those of magic realism. A tantric practitioner possessing *gnyan* 'power from a class of powerful deities capable of harming people if offended' protects a family's or a community's livestock. Lo was skeptical but later was convinced when his father suffered from such an experience. This belief was strengthened when Lo and his associates went on a failed bandit raid and witnessed firsthand such spiritual power when the bandits' family tried to steal yaks and chanted *tantra* spells, successfully protecting their livestock.

Another example of a valuable firsthand historical reference is Lo's account of the warlord Ma Bufang's troops:

...cavalrymen with guns and swords came to my home and forced us to collect taxes from our little Rdor jag Tribe. As the family of the tribal leader, we had to collect taxes from tribal members. I don't recall them doing anything for us except collecting taxes. We had to pay taxes on mdzo, horses, yaks, sheep, livestock skin, leather, wool, lambskin, and the cash we had on hand (82-83).

Of added historical value related to Ma Bufang is Lo's narrative of Tsha nag tribal men killing Ma's tax collectors. The tribal head visits Ma Bufang in person with the corpses of Ma's soldiers on mules to plead for forgiveness to protect his tribe at the risk of losing his head:

Ma Bufang listened, laughed loudly, and said, "Tsha nag leader! It's not a problem to cut off your heads. You are a leader with a low position. But you will be tortured before I cut off your head!"

"Sure, we're ready for that, but after our heads are cut off, please don't do anything to members of our Tsha nag home community," Dpal Idan said.

"I don't care much about that, but we will surely cut off your heads," Ma said.

"Please do whatever you like, but please think wisely before you cut off our heads."

"Why should I care much about that? I've beheaded many people," said Ma.

"You need to think carefully. The leader of the Bla brang area, Bla dpon a blo,¹ is my community's sworn friend, and the leader of the Nag chu area, Grags pa rgyal mtshan, is also my community's close sworn friend. Both will get involved if you cut off my head," Dpal Idan said.

Ma Bufang suddenly changed his mind and said, "Haha! I don't need your heads. I can't eat them nor wear them, but I need *mda'mo stong gis bshag dgos* (half of a family's property in compensation)" (110).

Stag 'bum rgyal's *Degeneration* (2012) depicts relationships (both peaceful and fierce) among three Tibetan tribes and their conflict with Ma Bufang's troops due to heavy taxation. A storyline featuring a tribal leader visiting Ma's headquarters in Khri ka (Guide) to settle disputes is nearly identical to Lo's account but has very different consequences.

In describing the tension between the warlord and the tribe, boundaries of political power and social structure, such as sworn friends who were strategic allies between communities, come into play as the tribal leader promises to pay Ma compensation but flees

¹ A pa a lo.

the area with his subordinate families. A new challenge to survive emerges with conflict with other tribes, and many of the livestock belonging to Lo's group die from disease, forcing a return to their homeland. These informative narratives provide historians with rich firsthand materials they would find nowhere else.

Lo also discusses pikas and marmots, hinting at the complex relationship between herders and wildlife. Children growing up on the grassland tried to kill pika or marmot for fun and meat while their parents scolded them for taking life. Fat marmot flesh was particularly valuable as a dietary supplement during famine.

Lo also reveals many details of his private life, including dating, revenge, and two marriages, providing more information on social structure and local traditions.

Lo's accounts end by leaving untouched critical events that occurred afterward, such as social unrest in 1958, famine in the early 1960s, the Cultural Revolution, and later political reforms, opening up, and improvement of community livelihood.

PART TWO: LCAGS MO BYAMS

Lcags mo byams' memories begin with the community members returning home from exile. The earliest thing she could remember was living in their native place in the 1940s. Her narrations focus on family, marriage, children, and women, providing an excellent supplement to Lo's accounts.

Lcags mo byams' life account starts with the tragic death of her father and brother, who died in the same year when she was eleven. She lived with her mother and a neighbor widow after returning from exile. She also describes the first marriage of her oldest sister, Gcod pa thar (1933), who attempted suicide by jumping off a cliff because she was so unhappy in her first marriage. Gcod pa thar would eventually become Lo's second wife:

Our parents would not agree to the divorce Gcod pa thar wanted [with her first husband]. She herded her husband's sheep almost every day and drove the sheep up on the mountain near our parents' camp. She would then visit our home. Father always kicked her out of the tent immediately and sent her back to her husband's

sheep. However, she would follow Father back home and wouldn't leave until he angrily beat and scolded her some more. Eventually, she would leave but look back sadly at our tent after washing her tearful face at the stream just below our camp. Even though our parents always sent her back to her husband's tent, she continued to come to our parents' tent whenever she was herding her husband's sheep (151).

Lcags mo byams' sister married a man from a wealthy family with over one hundred yaks and 500 sheep:

Everyone thought she was lucky, but she told me she had to get up early every morning and, together with a little girl, milk thirty yaks and churn the milk. She got up so early that she milked under the moonlight.

She said, "When there is no light from the moon, it is so dark that we guess the location of each milk yak. Regardless of the weather, we must get up at the same time and stick our warm bare feet into the cold-muddy area where the milk yaks are tied and where the ground is wet with yak urine or rain. The bones of our feet become ice cold as we milk with our head against a warm yak."

They milked under sparkling stars. She once went to sleep while she was milking. Fortunately, no one noticed. After driving the yaks to the mountains, they collected yak dung and carried it to their tent in a basket, which was heavier than a full water bucket (154).

Lcags mo byams further describes her marriage:

When I was fifteen, I was engaged to Rgya mtsho, the nephew of my adoptive mother's husband and Sha bo. I almost fainted when I heard that he was going to be my husband. I cried. He was ten years older than me. I said it was impossible and constantly sobbed to show my unhappiness. Chos lo reported how I felt and said she was worried about me and couldn't bear to see me so upset (155).

Her graphic commentary on the status of women in her youth includes details of illness and treatments from monks and tantric practitioners.

Major unrest in many Tibetan areas in 1958 was followed by "reforms," starvation, and the Cultural Revolution. Religious

practice was forbidden, community class struggles were carried out, and people worked in communal teams. Lcags mo byams notes:

Many rumors about the new government's army circulated just before a period of chaos in 1958. Locals often consulted Rdor jag Lha pa, who claimed that there was no need to worry, it was a brief storm, and people would soon see the blue sky and warm sun again. Locals felt relieved when they heard this (162).

Despite the tantric practitioner's positive prediction, Lcags mo byams recalls:

Rdor jag Lha pa's family was initially not required to farm. Instead, they were assigned to herd communal livestock because they had stayed behind while other locals had fled when soldiers came in 1958. People admired those who did light work, such as herding. Most locals had to do heavy work such as plowing grassland but received poor food.

However, Rdor jag Lha pa was soon accused of being a religious practitioner, and all of his family members were ordered to farm. Rdor jag Lha pa was told he would be publicly criticized the next day. He died after bellowing as loud as thunder that night. Locals thought this meant he was a great man because he had passed away before local women leaders humiliated him in public. Rdor jag Lha pa was special because he avoided women's punishment, which many *bla ma* experienced.

Rdor jag Lha pa's wife survived starvation and communal work and grew very old (162-163).

Lcags mo byams further authenticates living situations during different periods with her most recent story about Gcod pa thar giving birth to her last child at forty-three in the last year of the Cultural Revolution (1976).

DISCUSSION

The conception of "oral history" has evolved. Summerfield quotes Ronald Grele's definition in 1973 as "the interviewing of eyewitness participants in the events of the past for purposes of historical reconstruction" (2016:1). Consequently, "interviewing" is "eye

witness participants" providing the source of information and "historical reconstruction" is the purpose of oral history.

Oral history reliability has been criticized due to the fallibility of interviewees' memory and how accurately they represent the wider population. Scholars debate memory, narrative, subjectivity, value, and validity of oral evidence. Defenders of oral history maintain that despite constraints, "oral resources do not have a monopoly of such problems" (Summerfield 2016:3), and Portelli points out:

Oral sources are credible but with a different credibility. The importance of oral testimony may lie not in its adherence to fact, but rather in its departure from it, as imagination, symbolism, and desire emerge. Therefore, there are no 'false' oral sources (1998:68).

Summerfield writes:

Oral history today is less a quest for objective eyewitness accounts in which the narrator provides the historian with data for interpretation, and more a means to engage with experience, subjectivity, and historical imagination. ... Oral history is used as a research method in different ways and with varying emphases on "data" and "text" by a wide range of disciplines within academia and by a huge variety of organizations outside, from schools and community groups to voluntary organizations and hospitals (Summerfield 2016:1).

Oral history theorists and practitioners work to provide practical guidelines for oral history work: preparation for the interviewing project, interviewing methodology, data analysis and interpretation, legalities and ethics of oral history work, and transcription of oral history accounts (Perks and Thomson 1998; Yow 2005).

Having reviewed some basic theoretical criteria for oral history, we now turn to Klu thar rgyal's work and how he chose the subject and interviewees, conducted interviews, and transcribed the oral sources, thus significantly contributing to local history with the assistance of the other authors.

Writing oral history requires an author to have knowledge of the topic and be equipped to deal with inevitable challenges that arise. In choosing topics, interviewees, and intentions, the author writes:

...motivated by reading oral history accounts in *Asian Highlands Perspectives*, I spent time in 2016 and 2017 listening and learning more about Lo's long, extraordinary life, and the life of his second wife, my grandmother, Gcod pa thar, and the life and times of her sister, Lcags mo byams (29).

The author clearly intends to record the life histories of the mentioned two individuals (rather than particular historical events or a specific time frame of a regional history), who happened to be his relatives, which provides important advantages.

Lo's life story from childhood in the 1930s and ending in the 1950s includes descriptions of contemporary community life and important regional historical events, particularly by the Ma family. Approximately two-thirds of Lo's life remains untold.

Lcags mo byams' life story covers three decades from her childhood in the 1940s to the 1970s, leaving more than half of her life blank. Photos of the two interviewees' late life situations and brief sections describing their "current life" are provided.

The special relationship (relatives) and trust between the interviewer and interviewees suggests the interviews were conducted in an intimate, informal atmosphere, but there were challenges. When the author first approached Lo, he was met with: "Your questions remind me of the time I was detained, and soldiers asked what I had done each year since I was eight years old. I was told to confess everything" (33). The interviewer adjusted his approach promptly, clearing an unexpected interview obstacle.

Lo was reluctant to talk about his deceased wife, so the author wisely interviewed his maternal grandmother's sister, Lcags mo byams. These situations involve complex cultural and ethical issues that might negatively affect the interviews if inappropriately handled. Close association and mutual trust are great gifts during interviews, exemplified by the author obtaining information from other relatives to fill in missing information and cross-check the

accuracy of the information he obtained from the two main informants.

As eyewitnesses to events, an interviewee's testimonies are the backbone of creating oral history. What the interviewee told, or left untold, is essential. The theoretical development of oral history has shifted from the earlier stage of being "preoccupied with the accuracy of the information that interviewees provided and the reliability of memory" towards a "greater interest in the narratives people compose about the past and how memory is socially, culturally and psychically constructed," or "a shift from concern with data to concern with text (Summerfield:1-2).

This does not exclude the accuracy of an informant's information from examination. Lo's memory of people, places, and times of events was "phenomenal." Klu thar rgyal claims to have interviewed other relevant individuals, keenly listened to conversations between interviewees and others, asked questions seeking clarification, and visited places mentioned in the narrations to cross-check information his informants provided. Such efforts certainly increase the information's accuracy and credibility.

Yet, due to cultural constraints, personal memory limits, or the relationship between the two factors, subjectivity is the main feature of a personal account, which should not be judged solely by the accuracy of the data. Subjectivity characterizes an oral history's formulation.

How should collected oral resources be represented? Writing an oral history accurately is tedious and made more so by writing in a foreign language. Samuel describes certain challenges in oral history transcription:

The spoken word can very easily be mutilated when it is taken down in writing and transferred to the printed page. Some distortion is bound to arise, whatever the intention of the writer, simply by cutting out pauses and repetitions.....A much more serious distortion arises when the spoken word is boxed into the categories of written prose.....Continuity, and the effort to impose it even when it violates the twists and turns of speech, is another insidious influence.....The decadence of transcription may become extreme if the writer, not content with mutilating a text,

by cuts and rearrangements, then attempts to weave it together again with interpolated words of his own (1998:389).

In working to make his oral history as close to the original accounts as possible, Klu thar rgyal assembled inter-connected narratives into categories based on content, arranged them chronologically, and listened to them multiple times, which the narratives' chronological flow attests.

The author's generous use of photos, maps, charts, footnotes, livestock names, and Tibetan and Chinese terms in the text at the end significantly adds to the book's value.

Thompson suggests (which I paraphrase) the importance of oral history's value and impact:

In all these fields of history, by introducing new evidence from the underside, shifting the focus and opening new areas of inquiry, challenging historians' assumptions and accepted judgments, and bringing recognition to ignored people, a cumulative process of transformation is set in motion. This enlarges and enriches the scope of historical writing, changes its social message, and makes history more democratic (1998: 26).

A particular value of this oral history is modeling social and historical realities of regional communities at particular times via ordinary community members' accounts. This recognizes and values local knowledge, empowering the collective/community members otherwise ignored by historians. Thus, grassroots knowledge becomes essential to macro-level history creation.

Another significance of this book's contributions is the application of oral history research methodology to studies of Tibetan regions. Many researchers of Tibetan regions' history focus on written achievements. In contrast, *Last Memories* is an innovative approach to extending history beyond simply recording the memories of two individuals.

An oral history not only accurately records interviewees' accounts but is also expected to provide sufficient supplementary materials to verify informants' accounts, especially historical figures and events previously studied by scholars.

As mentioned earlier, missing parts of the interviewees' life stories, especially their perspectives on important issues and events, would make this oral history more complete. Another oral history from the same region may serve as a comparison. Nangchukja's (2015) detailed life history of a woman who was an eyewitness to important events in contemporary China organized in sections subtitled "1958:Chaos," "the Great Famine," and "the Cultural Revolution" in chronological order. Local official documents related to the event as supplemental information are cited. Nangchukja explains the value of the oral history he recorded:

Her life is just one example of the rich knowledge and experiences that contemporary Tibetan elders possess, a knowledge which is going largely unrecorded and unarchived and may be lost to the future were it not for concerted effort (2015:254).

CONCLUSION

Last Memories provides firsthand materials of a Tibetan community in the pre-1958 era based on two ordinary individuals' extraordinary experiences. This innovative treatment of local oral history features is important given that the number of Tibetans who experienced this period and can provide details of intimate lived experiences is rapidly diminishing. The community's social structure is better understood because it is built on the tumultuous series of events and rich ethnographical materials in the interviewees' accounts. *Last Memories* is an example of a social and historical study that was possible in the early 2020s based on individual lives providing an important contribution to a more inclusive historical picture of ethnic minority communities living in remote regions often overlooked by historians.

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TIBETAN TERMS

a mdo ཨ་མདོ།
 bla brang ལྷ་བང།
 bla dpon a blo ལྷ་དཔོན་ཨ་ལོ།
 bla ma ལྷ་མ།
 bu lo འུ་ལོ།
 chos lo ཚོས་ལོ།
 dpal ldan དཔལ་ལྷན།
 gcod pa thar གཙོད་པ་ཐར།
 gnyan གཉན།
 grags pa rgyal mtshan
 གཉགས་པ་རྒྱལ་མཚན།
 gser lag གསེར་ལག།
 kan lho ཀན་ལྷོ།
 khri ka ཁྲི་ཀ།
 klu thar rgyal ལྷ་ཐར་རྒྱལ།
 lcags mo byams ལྷགས་མོ་བྱམས།
 mang ra མང་ར།
 mda'mo stong gis bshag dgos
 མདའ་མོ་སྟོང་གིས་བཤག་དགོས།
 mdzo མཚོ།
 mgo log མགོ་ལོག།
 mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྟོན།
 mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
 nag chu རྟག་ཆུ།
 Nangchukja, snying lcags

rgyal རྒྱལ་ལྷགས་རྒྱལ།
 o rgyan ཨོ་རྒྱན།
 rdor jag lha pa རྫོང་རྟག་ལྷ་པ།
 reb gong རེབ་གོང།
 rgya mtsho རྒྱ་མཚོ།
 sha bo ཤ་བོ།
 thang nag ཐང་ནག།
 tsha nag ཚ་ནག།
 yul shul ཡུལ་ཤུལ།

CHINESE TERMS

Gannan 甘南
 Gansu 甘肃
 Gesangnuobu 格桑诺布
 Guomindang 国民党
 Guide 贵德
 Guinan 贵南
 Hainan 海南
 Hainan zangzu zizhizhou
 海南藏族自治州
 Ma Bufang 马步芳
 Qinghai 青海
 Sailihai 赛力亥
 Yushu 玉树